

LITERATURE REVIEW OF *MUSTAK* IN VARIOUS *AYURVEDIC* TREATISEMaurya Mamta^{*1}, Tripathi S. M.², Verma Simran¹, Singh Prashu¹^{*1}P.G Scholar, ²Professor

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ABSTRACT

Cyperus rotundus Linn., commonly known as nut grass or *Mustak*, a highly valued rhizome widely used in *Ayurvedic* medicines. The plant rhizomes have been traditionally employed in the treatment of various ailments, such as fever, diarrhoea, diabetes, piles, inflammation, obesity, and skin disorders. In *Ayurveda*, *Mustak* considered as potent herb due to its broad therapeutic properties and value. *Mustak* described under several *Ayurvedic* groups such as *Lekhaniya Mahakashaya*, *Triptighna Mahakashaya*, and *Kandughna Mahakashaya*. The *guna-karma* (properties and actions) are also explained as *laghu*, *ruksha guna*; *tikta*, *katu*, and *kashaya rasa*; *katu vipaka* and *sheet veerya*. *Mustak* indicated as an ingredient in numerous *Ayurvedic* formulations such as *Sadangapaneeya*, *Phaltrikadi kwath*, *Brahama Rasayan*, *Chavyanprash*, *Gangadhar churn*, *Chandraprabha Vati*, *Navayas lauh* and used in the treatment of *Jwar*, *Pipasa*, *Madhumeh*, *Kash*, *Sangrahani* and *Shoath*. The therapeutic importance of *Mustak* well defined in classical texts including the *Vedas*, *Samhitas*, *Kosha Granthas*, and various *Nighantus*.

KEYWORDS: *Cyperus rotundus* Linn, *Mustak*, Medicinal plant, *Ayurveda* herb, Sedge family (Cyperaceae).

INTRODUCTION

Cyperus rotundus Linn., commonly known as nut grass, purple nut sedge; *Musta*, *Mustak*, *Nagarmotha* in *Ayurveda*, a perennial herb under the Cyperaceae family.^[1] *Mustak*, typically flowers and fruits between June and October.^[2] The plant is distributed widely across India up to elevations of 1800 meters, from Kashmir to Shimla, Garhwal, and the Khasi Hills, as well as the plains and mountainous regions extending from Mount Abu and Pune to the Nilgiri Hills.^[3]

In classical *Ayurvedic* literature, *Mustak* is referred to by numerous synonyms, including *Jalad*, *Nagarmusta*, *Ghan*, *Shishira*, *Bhadra*, *Gudagranthi*, *Sugandhi*, *Hima*, *Varid*, *Gundra*.^[4] *Mustak* extensively described in major *Ayurvedic* texts such as the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Bhavaprakasha Samhita*, *Bhela Samhita*, *Harita Samhita*, and *Kashyapa Samhita*, and indicated with efficacy in treating “leprosy, fevers, thirst, blood diseases, dysentery, vomiting, epilepsy, ophthalmia, and antihelmintic”.^[5] *Mustak* is often recommended in *Pitta* and *Kapha*-related disorders, particularly in inflammation, fever, and metabolic disturbances. It is classified under *Lekhaniya*, *Triptighna*, *Kadughan*, *Stanyashodhan*, *Trishnanigrahan*, *Sangrahaneya*, *Deepaniya Dravya*, *Jwaraghana*, *Sothahar Mahakashaya*.^[6] In this article, a detailed literature review of *Mustak* has been covered and

compiled from *Samhitas*, *Nighantus*, *Rasa Granthas* as *Rastarangini* and *Rasaratnasamuccaya*. The ancient literature review, synonyms, formulations, with *Mustak*, its raspanchak and efficacy explained that the plant *Mustak* is highly potential, effective, commonly available, economical and widely accepted drug of *Ayurveda*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Mustak in *Samhita kala Charak Samhita*^[6]

Mustak has been referenced extensively in several chapters of the *Sutra Sthana* and *Chikitsa Sthana*, of the *Charaka Samhita*. Its use in a variety of disorders, as well as its inclusion as a key ingredient in numerous *Ayurvedic* formulations, highlights its therapeutic significance in classical *Ayurvedic* literature. The *Mustak* formulations and their indications are as follows.

S. NO	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF.NO
1.	<i>Musta swaras</i>	<i>Santarpan janya vyadi</i>	<i>Ca.Su.23/12</i>
2.	<i>Agraya dravaya</i>	<i>Sangrahi, Dipan, Pachan</i>	<i>Ca.Su.25/40</i>
3.	<i>Brahma Rasayan</i>	<i>Rasayan karma</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.1-1/48</i>
4.	<i>Chyavanprasa</i>	<i>Kasa, Shwasa,</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.1-1/64</i>
5.	<i>Indrokt rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayan karma</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.1-4/14</i>
6.	<i>Shadanga Paniya</i>	<i>Pipasa, Jwara</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.3/145</i>
7.	<i>Musta parpataka kashyaya</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.3/197</i>
8.	<i>Trayamanadya ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.5/119</i>
9.	<i>Asthapana Basti with sneha</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/46</i>
10.	<i>Mustadi churna</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/65</i>
11.	<i>Kanakbindvarista</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/77</i>
12.	<i>Siddharthaka snana</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/91</i>
13.	<i>Mustadi Taila</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/102</i>
14.	<i>Kanakakhsiri taila</i>	<i>Mandala Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/113</i>
15.	<i>Tiktashatpala ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/142</i>
16.	<i>Mahatiktaka ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.7/144</i>
17.	<i>Kshara Gudika</i>	<i>Svayathu</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.12/43</i>
18.	<i>Pippalyadi kshara</i>	<i>Udraroga</i>	<i>Ca. Ci 13/159</i>
19.	<i>Hriveradi Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.14/231</i>
20.	<i>Sunishannaka Changeri Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.14/236</i>
21.	<i>Chandanadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaja Grahani</i>	<i>Ca. Ci 15/126</i>
22.	<i>Nagaradya churna</i>	<i>Pittaja Grahani</i>	<i>Ca. Ci 15/129</i>
23.	<i>Kiratadya Churna</i>	<i>Grahani roga</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.15/138</i>
24.	<i>Mulasava</i>	<i>Dipana, Raktapitta</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.15/158</i>
25.	<i>Haridradya Kshara</i>	<i>Agnivardhnam</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.15/182</i>
26.	<i>Pancham Kshara</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.15/188</i>
27.	<i>Katukadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta, Jwara, Daha,</i>	<i>Ca.CI 16/47</i>
28.	<i>Vishaladi Phanta</i>	<i>Pandu roga</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.16/60</i>
29.	<i>Navayasa Churna</i>	<i>Pandu roga</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.16/70</i>
30.	<i>Mandurvataka</i>	<i>Pandu roga</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.16/73</i>
31.	<i>Punarnava mandura</i>	<i>Pandu roga</i>	<i>Ca. Ci. 16/94</i>
32.	<i>Vyoshadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Pandu roga</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.16/119</i>
33.	<i>Shatiyadi churna</i>	<i>Tamak Svasa, Hikka</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.17/123</i>
34.	<i>Duhsparshadi leha</i>	<i>Vatika Kasa</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.18/51</i>
35.	<i>Manahashiladi Dhuma</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.18/69</i>
36.	<i>Sharkaradi leha</i>	<i>Kasa caused by pitta</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.18/90</i>
37.	<i>Tvagadi leha</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Ca. Ci. 18/92</i>
38.	<i>Jivantyadi leha</i>	<i>All five varieties of Kasa</i>	<i>Ca.Ci.18/176</i>

Sushruta Samhita^[7]

In *Sushruta Samhita*, *Mustak* is also described in various therapeutic contexts and uses. *Acharya Sushruta* provides a detailed account of its pharmacological

properties and medicinal actions for different ailments. The text documents the use of *Mustak* in the treatment of several disorders and its inclusion as an ingredient in numerous *Ayurvedic* formulations as follows.

S. NO	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF.NO
1.	<i>Trivrtastaka modaka</i>	<i>Pittaja vyadhi</i>	<i>Su.Su.44/54</i>
2.	<i>Vardhamana pippali yoga</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Su.Ci.5/12</i>
3.	<i>Mahatiktaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Su.Ci.9/8</i>
4.	<i>Tiktaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Su.Ci.9/9</i>
5.	<i>Navayasa loha</i>	<i>Shofa</i>	<i>Su.Ci 12/11</i>
6.	<i>Dashmuladi basti</i>	<i>Kaphaja roga,</i>	<i>Su.Ci.38/64</i>
7.	<i>Sanshamana basti</i>	<i>Dosha Shamana</i>	<i>Su.Ci.38/95</i>
8.	<i>Mustadi raja yapana basti</i>	<i>Vatarakta, Prameha etc.</i>	<i>Su.Ci.38/106</i>
9.	<i>Tarkasya Agada</i>	<i>Taksaka Sarpa visha</i>	<i>Su.Ka.5/65</i>
10.	<i>Maha sugandhi agada</i>	<i>Sarpa visha</i>	<i>Su.Ka.6/19</i>
11.	<i>Mustadi Kwatha</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Su.Ut.39/208</i>
12.	<i>Kalyanaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Jirna Jwara</i>	<i>Su.Ut.39/229</i>

13.	<i>Panchgavya Ghrita</i>	<i>Vishama Jwara</i>	<i>Su.Ut.39/241</i>
14.	<i>Kalyanaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Su.Ut.62/22</i>

Astangahrdaya^[8] (7th century A.D.)

In *Ashtanghridaya Samhita*, *Mustak* is described under *Kaphagna gana*, *Mustadi Gana*, *Vachadi Gana* and *Tikata gana*. The *Acharyas* rigorously observed the

pharmacological properties and actions of *Mustak* and introduced it as an ingredient in different formulations as follows.

S.NO	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Drakshadi phanta</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.1/56</i>
2.	<i>Pippalyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.1/90</i>
3.	<i>Mustadi Basti</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.1/120, 122</i>
4.	<i>Kasamardadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa Shosha, Jvara, Pliha roga,</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.3/162</i>
5.	<i>Jivantyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Parshvaruka, Jvara, Kasa, Hikka</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.4/43</i>
6.	<i>Trayamanadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vidradhi</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.13/15</i>
7.	<i>Tikta Ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.19/4</i>
8.	<i>Mahatiktaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.19/10</i>
9.	<i>Bala Taila</i>	<i>Vata Vyadhi</i>	<i>Ah.Ci.21/76</i>
10.	<i>Siddha Basti</i>	<i>Vatarakta, Moha etc.</i>	<i>Ah. Ka. 4/37</i>
11.	<i>Patoladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Shukra, Timira, Naktandhya,</i>	<i>Ah.Ut.13/8</i>
12.	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Karna Badhirya</i>	<i>Ah.Ut.18/28</i>
13.	<i>Bramha Rasayana</i>	<i>Tandra, Shrama, Klama</i>	<i>Ah.Ut.39/17</i>
14.	<i>Cyavanaprasha</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa etc.</i>	<i>Ah.Ut.39/33</i>
15.	<i>Agyasangraha</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	<i>Ah.Ut.40/48</i>

Astangasangraha^[9] (7th century A.D.)

In *Astangasangraha Samhita*, *Mustak* has been mentioned in different contexts. *Acharya Vagbhata*

thoroughly observed the pharmacological properties and actions of *Mustak* and recommended in various disorders and as an ingredient in different formulations as follows.

S.NO	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF.NO
1.	<i>Anu Taila</i>	<i>Keshya, Tvachya, Kanthya,</i>	<i>As.Su.29/9</i>
2.	<i>Kalyanaka Kshara</i>	<i>Garvisha</i>	<i>As.Ci.10/51</i>
3.	<i>Agastya ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	<i>As.Ci.12/9</i>
4.	<i>Dashmulasava</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	<i>As.Ci.12/15</i>
5.	<i>Mahatiktaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>As.Ci.21/4</i>
6.	<i>Raj yapana basti</i>	<i>Asragdara, Unmada, Shoph</i>	<i>As.Ka.5/10</i>
7.	<i>Ghrita yoga</i>	<i>Balgraha</i>	<i>As. U. 4/10</i>
8.	<i>Sanjivana agada</i>	<i>Visha chikitsa</i>	<i>As.U.40/59</i>
9.	<i>Yapana agada</i>	<i>Visha chikitsa</i>	<i>As.U.40/68</i>
10.	<i>Brahma rasayana</i>	<i>Tandra, shrama, klama</i>	<i>As.U.49/26</i>
11.	<i>Cyavana prakasha</i>	<i>Kasa, shvasa</i>	<i>As.U.49/39</i>

Sharangdhara^[10] (13th century A.D)

In *Sharangdhara Samhita*, *Mustak* has also been

described in different contexts, and indicated in various disorders and as an ingredient of various formulations.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Katphaladi kwath</i>	<i>Pttaj jwar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/12</i>
2.	<i>Panchbhadra kwath</i>	<i>Vatptaj jwar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/20</i>
3.	<i>Abhayadi kwath</i>	<i>Sannipat jwar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/32-34</i>
4.	<i>Katphaladi kwath</i>	<i>Hikka, kas, jwar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/43</i>
5.	<i>Devdardadi kwath</i>	<i>Prasuta stri shool, kas,jwar, murchha</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/47-49</i>
6.	<i>Nagaradi kwath</i>	<i>Jwaratarisar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/61</i>
7.	<i>Hiberadi kwath</i>	<i>Jeern atisar, jwar</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/67-68</i>
8.	<i>Triphaladi kwath</i>	<i>Krimi</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/74</i>
9.	<i>Phaltrikadi kwath</i>	<i>Prameh</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/109</i>
10.	<i>Davryadi kwath</i>	<i>Prader</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/110</i>
11.	<i>Vasadi kawath</i>	<i>Swarbhed,Pinas,Swas</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/146-147</i>
12.	<i>Sadangpaniya</i>	<i>Pipasa, Jwar, Daah</i>	<i>Sh.Ma.kh.2/158</i>

13.	Navayas churn	Pandurog,Hridayarog,Bhagandar, Shoth	Sha.Ma.kh.6/161-163
14.	Bahushal gud	Gulm, Vatjanit udar rog, Aamvat	Sh.Ma.kh.7/6-12
15.	Mandur vatak	Kamla,Pandu,prameh, shoth	Sh.Ma.kh.7/34-36
16.	Chandraprabha vati	Prameh, Mutraghat, Mutrakrich	Sh.Ma.kh.7/40-49
17.	Triphala Modak	Kusth, Vat,pitta,kaph rog, Bhagandar,pleeha, gulm	Sh.Ma.kh.7/88-94
18.	Kantkari Avaleh	Hikka,shwas,kas	Sh.Ma.kh.8/5-9
19.	Kasisadi ghrita	Kustha, Dadru, Pama, Visharp	Sh.Ma.kh.9/51-57
20.	Phalagrita	Bandya,Shukradosh, Artavdosh	Sh.Ma.kh.9/51-57
21.	Marichyadi tail	Kusth, Vicharchika,Shwetakusth	Sh.Ma.kh.9/148-152
22.	Vacha tail	Gandmala	Sh.Ma.kh.9/192-194
23.	Kumaryasav	Dhatuwardhak, Shukrardhak, Kshayrog, Udar rog, Prameh	Sh.Ma.kh.10/20-29
24.	Dashmularist	Grahani,Shwas,Kas,Gulm,Bhagandar,	Sh.Ma.kh.10/79-94

Bhavaprakasa^[11] (16th century A.D.)

Bhavaprakasa Samhita, the Mustak has been described in different contexts and formulation. Acharya minutely

observes the pharmacological properties and actions of Mustak and describe as an ingredient in different formulations as follows.

S. N	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	Sudarshan churn	Ras rakkadi dhatugat jwar, Mnas jwar	Bha.Ci.1/125-135
2.	Drakshadi kwath	Mukhshos, Pralap, peeda, Daah,	Bha.Ci.1/344-345
3.	Mahadrakshadi kwath	Jwar, Dah, Pralap, Raktpit,Bhram	Bha.Ci.1/352-355
4.	Kantkaryadi kwath	Pittakaphaj jwar, Daah, Aruchi, vaman,	Bha.Ci.1/432-433
5.	Nagaradi kwath	Pittakaph jwar, Grahi	Bha.Ci.1/434
6.	Astardashang kwath	Snnipat jwar, pralap,Tandra, Aruchi,	Bha.Ci.1/578
7.	Mustadi kwath	Pralapak, Snnipat jwar	Bha.Ci.1/647
8.	Kakadashrigyadi kwath	Prameh, Karnshool, Sannipat jwar,	Bha.Ci.1/658
9.	Vachadi kwath	Sannipat jwar, Bhram, Pakshaghat	Bha.Ci.1/662
10.	Kiratkatukadi kwath	Kanthkubaj sannipat jwar	Bha.Ci.1/694
11.	Drakshapatoladi	Anyedhusak visam jwar	Bha.Ci.1/764
12.	Dwatrinsatkwath	Sannipat,jwar,Gudrog,Shwas,Hridayarog,	Bha.Ci.1/846
13.	Vatsakadi kwath	Atisar,Amatisar,Raktastisar	Bha.Ci.2/22
14.	Dhanyadipanchakkwath	Amashool,Vibandha,deepak	Bha.Ci.2/23
15.	Gangadhar kwath	Pravahyukt atisar	Bha.Ci.2/29
16.	Bilvadi kwath	Aamdoshyukt pittaj atisar	Bha.Ci.2/46
17.	Kutajadi kwath	Raktatisardaah, shool, atisar	Bha.Ci.2/52-53
18.	Chatusamamodak	Sampurn atisar, aamaatisar, vibandha	Bha.Ci.2/88-89
19.	Vrihatguduchiyadi kwath	Aruchi,Trishna,Daah,Vaman	Bha.Ci.3/10
20.	Bahushal gud	Udar rog, Gulm, Prameh,Pandu,	Bha.Ci.5/81-90
21.	Brihadagnimukh churn	Ajeern, Gulm,Pleeha,Antravidhi,udar	Bha.Ci.6/45-52
22.	Asthadashang lauh	Pandu, Halimak, Shoth, Prameh, Grahani,Shwas rog	Bha.Ci.8/35-38
23.	Navayas lauh	Pandu, Shoth, Hridya rog, Udar rog,	Bha.Ci.8/55-57
24.	Narikelkhand	Amlapit, Raktapita, Kshay, Parinam shool	Bha.Ci.10/23-26
25.	Vrihannarikel khand	Amlapita,Jwar,Raktapit,Vatrakt,	Bha.Ci.10/27-35
26.	Eladichurn	Kaph,Vaat, pitaj vaman	Bha.Ci.18/15
27.	Punarnavadg tail	Ashmari, Mutrakrichh, Antravidhi	Bha. Ci. 37/ 95-99
28.	Gokshuradi churn	Prameh, Shoth, Arsh, Pandu, Halimak	Bha.Ci 38/81-87
29.	Laghumarichyadi tail	Shwitrakusth,Kandu,pama, Siddhma,Vicharchika,pundrik	Bha.Ci.54/ 107-111
30.	Adarakakhand	Deepan,Vaatgulm,Kas,Shwas,	Bha.Ci.54/ 115-117

Bhela Samhita^[12]

Bhela Samhita, described Mustak in different contexts as well as in the formulations. Acharya Bhel thoroughly observed the pharmacological properties and actions of Mustak and recommended in the formulations as ingredients such as Mustadi kwath (Bhel.Ci.12/6), Dashmuladi tail (Bhel.Ci.14/18), Changeri ghritam

(Bhel.Ci.16/39-50), Rasna tail (Bhel. Ci.24/29-31), Vibhitakadi churn (Bhel. Ci.24/29-31).

Harita Samhita^[13]

The use of Mustak in various disorders and as an ingredient in various formulations were found in Harita Samhita as mentioned follows.

S.NO	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF.NO
1.	<i>Panchabhadra kwatha</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>H.S.3/2/89</i>
2.	<i>Sunthyadi kwatha</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>H.S.3/2/91</i>
3.	<i>Panchmoola kwatha</i>	<i>Vatika Jwara</i>	<i>H.S.3/2/162</i>
4.	<i>Kutaja Putpaka</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>H.S.3/3/29</i>
5.	<i>Kaligadi kalka</i>	<i>Raktaatisara</i>	<i>H.S.3/3/52</i>
6.	<i>Vatsakadi kwatha</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>H.S.3/3/53</i>
7.	<i>Darkshadi pindi</i>	<i>Pittaja Grahani</i>	<i>H.S.3/3/105</i>
8.	<i>Hingavadi kwatha</i>	<i>Shoola</i>	<i>H.S.3/7/26</i>
9.	<i>Brijamanduka vataka</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>H.S.3/8/25</i>
10.	<i>Bhallataka avaleha</i>	<i>Gudaroga</i>	<i>H.S.3/11/80</i>
11.	<i>Katphaladi kwatha</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>H.S.3/12/28</i>

***Kasyapa Samhita*^[14] (600-1000B.C)**

Kasyapa Samhita considered one of the also oldest classical texts of *Ayurveda*. *Mustak* has been described as an ingredient in multiple formulations such as *Katuka sarpi* (*Kas.Ka.8/141*), *Phala taila* (*Kas.Khi.8/92*), *Eranda basti* (*Kas.Khi.8/100*).

***Siddhasara Samhita*^[15] (7th century A.D.)**

The author of this manuscript *Acharya Ravigupta*, has described *Mustak* in various disorders and as an ingredient of formulations as in following chart.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Vachadi gana</i>	<i>Amatisar, Pachan, Stanyadosh</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.2:26</i>
2.	<i>Mustadi gana</i>	<i>Vatnashak, Hridhya, Trishnahar</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.2:41-42</i>
3.	<i>Vatsakadi ghrut</i>	<i>Kshay, Dah, Kas, Halimak</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.5:91-92</i>
4.	<i>Dhavaniyadi tail</i>	<i>Sarvjwar, vatvikar</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.5:98-100</i>
5.	<i>Lakshadi tail</i>	<i>Jwar, kashayrog, Unmad</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.5:117-119</i>
6.	<i>Dahtrishnahar tail</i>	<i>Trishnahar, Dah</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.5:124-126</i>
7.	<i>Vatasakadi churn</i>	<i>Grahani, Kamla, Prameh, Atisar</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.6:68-69</i>
8.	<i>Shigrudarvyadi kwath</i>	<i>Krimi</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.6:76</i>
9.	<i>Chandanadi Paniya</i>	<i>Raktpita</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.7:7</i>
10.	<i>Raktapitta nasak ghrut</i>	<i>Basti, Anjjan, Navan</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.7:23-24</i>
11.	<i>Laghu chayavanprash</i>	<i>Hridrog, Kas, Shwas, Vatrakt</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.8:26-31</i>
12.	<i>Triphladi kwath</i>	<i>Prameh</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.11:12</i>
13.	<i>Kaphshoolhar yog</i>	<i>Udavart, Kaphjanya shool</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.21:15</i>
14.	<i>Kaphjvisharp lep</i>	<i>Kaphjanya visharp</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.23:13</i>
15.	<i>Ghanadi gana</i>	<i>Stanyashuddhi</i>	<i>Sid.Sa.29:34</i>

Mustak in other Ayurvedic treatise***Vaidyaprasarakam*^[16] (9th century A.D.)**

This unique treatise was written by *Vaidya Acharya*

Gadadhara and he observed the pharmacological properties and actions of *Mustak* in various disorders and formulations.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Devdarushtak</i>	<i>Pravahika, Atop, Jwar, Atisar</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag.17</i>
2.	<i>Mustachatuskam</i>	<i>Trishnahar, pittajwarshamak</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:23</i>
3.	<i>Durvadyam</i>	<i>Sannipat jwar, Gulm, Raktapitta</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:56</i>
4.	<i>Mustatrikam</i>	<i>Sarvjwar, Atisar, Hrilas</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:58</i>
5.	<i>Panchkarsham</i>	<i>Vatajwar, kaphajwar</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:69</i>
6.	<i>Shunthyadyam</i>	<i>Jwar, Atisar, Gulm</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:72</i>
7.	<i>Pathadyam</i>	<i>Gudrog, Atisar, Raktdosh</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:114</i>
8.	<i>Dashango guggul</i>	<i>Kaph, Vaat, Tridoshaj vikar</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:131</i>
9.	<i>Saptvinshati guggul</i>	<i>Gulm, Pleeha, Udar, Arsh, Bhagandar, Shosh, Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:137</i>
10.	<i>Abhyadh Gutika</i>	<i>Arsh, Mudhvaat</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:182</i>
11.	<i>Gudtrikatukam</i>	<i>Ajeern, Kas, Kshay, Shosh, Panduta</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:195</i>
12.	<i>Vyoshadyam</i>	<i>Mutrakrich, Jwar, Vaman, Shwas</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:196</i>
13.	<i>Madhutailika vastaya</i>	<i>Vatrakt, Moh, Aondvridhi</i>	<i>Vai.Pr.1: pag:401</i>

***Chikitsakalika*^[17] (10th century A.D.)**

It is an important treatise written by *Tistacharya* he was

the son of *Vagbhata*. In this treatise many formulations with *Mustak* in various disorders and formulations has

been described. Mustak mentioned in *Chikitsakalika* formulation such as *Pippalyadi ghr̥it* (*Chi.Ka.2:120*) *Mandoor vatak* (*Chi.Ka.19:222-223*), *Saptvinshati guggul* (*Chi.Ka.25:258-260*), *Chayavanprash rasyan* (*Chi.Ka.28:266-269*).

Vaidyarahashya^[18] (13th Century A.D.)

Vaidyarahashya is a popular treatise written by *Bhishgavara Vidyapati*. In this treatise *Mustak* has been described in different formulations as an ingredient for the treatment of various disorders as follows.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Drakshadi kwath</i>	<i>Trishna, Murchha, Jwar, Dah</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.1:51</i>
2.	<i>Heeveradi kwath</i>	<i>Vaman, Trishna, Jwar, Dah</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.1:54</i>
3.	<i>Shringyadi kwath</i>	<i>Sannipat jwar, Mutrakrichha, Dah</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.1:92-97</i>
4.	<i>Dhanyapanchak</i>	<i>Shool, Vibandh, Mandagni</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.2:14</i>
5.	<i>Kutajavaleh</i>	<i>Amlapitt, Atisar, Pandurog</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.6:38-45</i>
6.	<i>Navayas churn</i>	<i>Kusth, Udar, Mandagni</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.9:12</i>
7.	<i>Eladi churn</i>	<i>Vataj, Pittaj, Tridoshaj, Chhardi</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.17:9</i>
8.	<i>Vartiktadi kwath</i>	<i>Vatvyadhi</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.21:14</i>
9.	<i>Rasnadi kwath</i>	<i>Pakshaghat, Ardit, Grahdasi, Hanugrah</i>	<i>Vd.Rh.21:35</i>
10.	<i>Yograj guggul</i>	<i>Aamvat, Apasmar, Kusth, Vatrakt, Krimi</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.21:99-108</i>
11.	<i>Chandraprabha vati</i>	<i>Pandu, SHool, Kaiishool, Anah, Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.34:4-8</i>
12.	<i>Pugpak</i>	<i>Veeryavardhak, Raktpradar</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.34:21-23</i>
13.	<i>Marichyadi tail</i>	<i>Pama, Kandu, Shidhm, Vicharchika</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.51:46-50</i>
14.	<i>Avipatkar churn</i>	<i>Malvibandh, Kosthbadhhata, Aamvat</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.54:12-14</i>
15.	<i>Kiratatikatadi kwath</i>	<i>Visphot, Vatrakt</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.55:3-4</i>
16.	<i>Triphala kwath</i>	<i>Timir, Kanch, Andhya</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.58:51</i>
17.	<i>jeerakavleh</i>	<i>Pradar, Aruchi, Shwas, Trishna</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.64:9-12</i>
18.	<i>Saubhagyashunthi avleh</i>	<i>Sutika</i>	<i>Vaid.Rh.65:20-25</i>

Vaidyajivanam^[19] (16-17th Century A.D.)

Vaidyajivanam by *Lolimbaraja* described in verse with shringar ras of different diseases and principles. In this

treatise *Mustak* has been described in different formulations as an ingredient for the treatment of various disorders as follows.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Panchmulyadi kwath</i>	<i>Vatapittaja jwara</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.1:34</i>
2.	<i>Katphaladi kwath</i>	<i>Kaphaj jwar, Kas, Mukhrog</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.1:38</i>
3.	<i>Patoladi kwath</i>	<i>Visham jwar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.1:63</i>
4.	<i>Kulkadi kwath</i>	<i>Vishasam jwar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.1:64</i>
5.	<i>Amritadi kwath</i>	<i>Atisar, Jwaratisar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.2:1</i>
6.	<i>Panchmuladi kwath</i>	<i>Jwaratisar, Vaman, Kas, Shwas, Shool</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.2:3</i>
7.	<i>Devdaruadi kwath</i>	<i>Atisar, Shokatisar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.2:5</i>
8.	<i>Kutajadi kwath</i>	<i>Raktatisar, Aamatisar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.2:11</i>
9.	<i>Pathadi churn</i>	<i>Raktatisar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.2:20</i>
10.	<i>Adrakpak</i>	<i>Kas, Arsh, Bhagandar, Jwar, Gulm, Peenas</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.3:36</i>
11.	<i>Pradarpratikarmah</i>	<i>Udararog, Pradar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.3:34</i>
22.	<i>Dhanyadi kwath</i>	<i>Garbhani, Raktatisar, Aamatisar</i>	<i>Vaid.Jee.3:46</i>

Arkaprakash^[20]

Arkaprakasha a popular treatise by *Ravana*. In this book a lot of formulations are described. As named, this treatise covered *Arka* (tincture) *Chikitsa*. The *Arka* obtained from medicines have been used in the treatment of various diseases. *Mustak* has been described under *Ajeernashakark* (*Arka.5:19*), *Haleemakrognasakark* (*Arka.5:31*), *Trishaghnoark* (*Arka.5:52*), *Rajoavrogharark* (*Arka.7:74*), *Skandapasmaraharark* (*Arka.7:7984*).

formulations from different books and *Samhitas*. There are numerous therapeutic formulations under different *adhikar varga* of diseases. It is used as reference book for formulations and the formulation having *Mustak* are as follows.

Bhaisajyaratnavali^[21] (18th Century A.D.)

This book is a highly acclaimed *Ayurvedic* treatise written by *Govinda Das* for specialized compilation of

S. N	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Drakshadi kwath</i>	<i>Pitajwar, Pralap, Mukhshosh, Daah</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/95-96</i>
2.	<i>Ghanachandanadi kwath</i>	<i>Jwar, Vaman, Aruchi, Daah</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/156</i>
3.	<i>Panchbhadradi kwath</i>	<i>Vaat pitta jwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/157</i>
4.	<i>Kantikaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Pittashwesmaj jwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/166-167</i>
5.	<i>Vrihadkatphaladi kwath</i>	<i>Gandmala, Swarbheda, Kaphavaatjwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/248-251</i>
6.	<i>Tagaradi kwath</i>	<i>Pralapak sannipat jwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/276</i>
7.	<i>Patoladi kwath</i>	<i>Visham jwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/340</i>
8.	<i>Sudarshan churn</i>	<i>Jwar, Pleeha, Yakritvridhi,</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/446-457</i>
9.	<i>Jwar bharav churn</i>	<i>Visham jwar, Satatasantatadi, Manas</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/446-457</i>
10.	<i>Agnikumar ras</i>	<i>Aamjwar, Kaphajwar, Peenas, Pratisyay</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/530-535</i>
11.	<i>Sarvjwarhar lauh</i>	<i>Vaataj, Pittaj, Kaphaj jwar</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/1153-1157</i>
12.	<i>Lohasav</i>	<i>Aganivardhak, pandu, shoth, gulm,</i>	<i>Bh.R.5/1235-1238</i>
13.	<i>Laghupanch mulayadi kwath</i>	<i>Atisar, jwar, chhardi, shoolyukt atisar, shwas rog</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/15-16</i>
14.	<i>Kiratiktadi kwath</i>	<i>Aamatisar, jwaratisar</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/27</i>
15.	<i>Vidangadi kwath</i>	<i>Jwaratisar, aamatisar, shoth</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/29</i>
16.	<i>Shunthadi kwath</i>	<i>Jwaratisar, aamatisar</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/29</i>
17.	<i>Kutajavaleh</i>	<i>Atisar, Grahani, Raktatisar, Pravahika</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/44-49</i>
18.	<i>Amritarvan ras</i>	<i>Atisar, grahani dosh, arsh, amlapitt</i>	<i>Bh.R.6/88-93</i>
19.	<i>Shothghnyadi kwath</i>	<i>Shothyukt atisar</i>	<i>Bh.R.7/77</i>
20.	<i>Chaturbhadradi kwath</i>	<i>Grahi, Agnideepak, Aamdosh</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/12</i>
21.	<i>Gangadhar churn</i>	<i>Atisar, Grahani Shool, Sutikarog,</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/43-45</i>
22.	<i>Lavangadi vati</i>	<i>Jwar, Atisar, Grahani, Mandagni</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/64-74</i>
23.	<i>Jeerakadi churn</i>	<i>Grahani, Atisar, Aamatisar</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/108-112</i>
24.	<i>Mundyadi gutika</i>	<i>Vaataj, Pittaj, Kaphaj grahni</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/127-130</i>
25.	<i>Kanchta avleh</i>	<i>Atisar, Sangrahani, Amlapitt, Udar rog</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/131-135</i>
26.	<i>Methi modak</i>	<i>Sangrahani, Prameh, Mutraghat</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/171-177</i>
27.	<i>Mustakadi modak</i>	<i>Sangrahani, Atisar, Darun, Paandurog</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/185-191</i>
28.	<i>Panchamrit mandur</i>	<i>Grahani, Atisar, Shoth, Pandu</i>	<i>Bh.R.8/528-534</i>
29.	<i>Mustakrist</i>	<i>Ajeern, Agnimand, Visuchika, Grahni</i>	<i>Bh.R.10/269-272</i>
30.	<i>Parshiyadi churn</i>	<i>Kas, Jwar, Ugratisar, Vaman</i>	<i>Bh.R.11/15</i>
31.	<i>Haridrakhanda</i>	<i>Sheetpitt, Dustvran, Kusth, Naadivran</i>	<i>Bh.R.11/51-58</i>
32.	<i>Paribhadradi avleh</i>	<i>Krimi, Shool, Vaman, Mandagni</i>	<i>Bh.R.11/51-65</i>
33.	<i>Vrihat vasa avleh</i>	<i>Raktapitt, Vataj, Pittaj Shwas</i>	<i>Bh.R.14/40-45</i>
34.	<i>Swalpchandandadi tail</i>	<i>Rajyakshma, Kas, Gardosh</i>	<i>Bh.R.14/282-285</i>
35.	<i>Vijay bhairav ras</i>	<i>Kas, Shwas, Kshay, Gulm, Prameh,</i>	<i>Bh.R.15/80-83</i>
36.	<i>Nagaradi churn</i>	<i>Atisar, Agnimand, Visuchika,</i>	<i>Bh.R.18/25-31</i>

Mustak in Rasa Grantha Rasaratnasamuchchaya^[22]

Rasaratnasamuchchaya a very important treatise by *Vagbhata*, but evidently, he is another *Vagbhata*, and has

no any concern with *Ashtanga Hrdaya* or *Ashtanga Sangraha*. *Mustak* mentioned as an ingredient of various formulations for the treatment of different ailments.

S.N.	PREPARATION	INDICATION	REF. NO
1.	<i>Sharangsathadi varg</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>R.R.S.12:90-91</i>
2.	<i>Chandrakala ras</i>	<i>Antardah, Vahadah, Raktashrav, Raktpit</i>	<i>R.R.S.13:5-8</i>
3.	<i>Neelkanth ras</i>	<i>Raktpit</i>	<i>R.R.S.13:60</i>
4.	<i>Hansmandoor</i>	<i>Pandu, Halimak, Urustambh, Kamla, Arsh</i>	<i>R.R.S.19:42-44</i>
5.	<i>Pitapanduvariras</i>	<i>Pitta, Pandu</i>	<i>R.R.S.19:75-76</i>
6.	<i>Kameshwar ras</i>	<i>Shoth, Pandu</i>	<i>R.R.S.21:98-101</i>
7.	<i>Yograj guggul</i>	<i>Aamvat, Adhyavat, Udar rog, Anah, Arsh</i>	<i>R.R.S.21:141-146</i>
8.	<i>Rasendrachudamani ras</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>R.R.S.27:85-94</i>
9.	<i>Madan Modak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>R.R.S.27:116-126</i>
10.	<i>Lauh kalp</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>R.R.S.28:35-51</i>
11.	<i>Kandvishanam</i>	<i>Vish</i>	<i>R.R.S.29:12-13</i>
12.	<i>Chandanadi tail</i>	<i>Nadi vran, Apachi</i>	<i>R.R.S.31:76-77</i>
13.	<i>Jayagudikakhyo vishkalp</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>R.R.S.31:117-118</i>

Rasatarangini^[23]

Mustak has been described in *Rasatarangini* for processing and trituration of limited formulations such as

Abhrak bhasm (R.T.10:38), *Lauh bhasm* (R.T.20:108), *Mandur bhasm* (R.T.21:138).

Classification of *Mustak* in different *Nighantus*

Sr.	<i>Nighantu</i>	<i>Gana/Varga</i>	Reference
1.	<i>Sausruta Nighantu</i> ^[24]	<i>Vachadi gana</i>	<i>Su.Ni. Vachadigana</i> : 188 (pg.56)
2.	<i>Astanga Nighantu</i> ^[25]	<i>Vachadi-Haridradi Gana</i>	<i>As.Ni Vachadi-Haridradi gana</i> :151 (pg.60)
3.	<i>Paryayaratanamala</i> ^[26]	Not included in any <i>Gana</i>	<i>Pary</i> :112 (pg.33)
4.	<i>Dhanwantari-Nighantu</i> ^[27]	<i>Guducyadi</i>	<i>Dh.Ni.Guduchyadi varga</i> :36-41(pag-23)
5.	<i>Shodhal-Nighantu</i> ^[28]	<i>Guducyadi Varga</i>	<i>Sho. Ni. Guduchyadi varga</i> :125(pg.27)
6.	<i>Abhidhan Ratnamala</i> ^[29]	<i>Kasayadravya Skand</i>	<i>Abi.Rat.Kasayadravya skand</i> :9 (pg.92)
7.	<i>Hridayadipaka-Nighantu</i> ^[30]	<i>Dvipada-Varga</i>	<i>Hr.ni.Dvipadavarga</i> :52(pag-32)
8.	<i>Madanapala-Nighantu</i> ^[31]	<i>Abhayadi</i>	<i>Mad. Pa.ni.Abhayadi varga</i> :210(pag-137)
9.	<i>Raj-Nighantu</i> ^[32]	<i>Pippalyadi Varga</i>	<i>Raj.Ni.Pipalyadi varga</i> :141-143 (pg.131)
11.	<i>Kaiyadeva-Nighantu</i> ^[33]	<i>Oshadhi Varga</i>	<i>Kai.Ni.Oshadhi varga</i> :1359-1361(pag-252)
12.	<i>Bhavprakash-Nighantu</i> ^[34]	<i>Karpuradi Varga</i>	<i>Bha.Ni.Karpuradi varga</i> :92-93 (pg.232)
13.	<i>Gunaratanmala</i> ^[35]	<i>Karpuradi Sugandha Varga</i>	<i>Gu.Rat.Karpuradi Sugandh.pg</i> .118
14.	<i>Sarwati Nighantu</i> ^[36]	<i>Chandanadi Varga</i>	<i>Sar. Ni. Chandanadi varga</i> :34 (pg.69)
15.	<i>Laghu-Nighantu</i> ^[37]	Not included in any <i>Gana</i>	<i>La. Ni slok</i> .96 (pg.24)
16.	<i>Paryayamuktavali</i> ^[38]	<i>Jeerakadi Madhyagandha Varga</i>	<i>Par. Mu. Jeerakadi Madhyagandh varga</i> :8 (pg.14)
17.	<i>Shaligram-Nighantu</i> ^[39]	<i>Karpuradi Varga</i>	<i>Sha.Ni.Karpuradi Varga</i> (pag-55)
18.	<i>Nighantu-Adarsh</i> ^[40]	<i>Mustadi Varga</i>	<i>Ni.A.Mustadi.pg</i> .707
19.	<i>Shankara-Nighantu</i> ^[41]	No any description of <i>Gana</i>	<i>Sha.ni.Nagarmotha</i> (pag-141)
20.	<i>Abhidhanamanjari</i> ^[42]	<i>Madanadigana Varga</i>	<i>Abhi.Man.Madanadigana varga.pg</i> -81
21.	<i>Priya-Nighantu</i> ^[43]	<i>Shatapushpadi</i>	<i>Pr.Ni.Shatpuspadi varga</i> :42(pag-82)

Sanskrit synonyms of *Mustak* described in different *Nighantus*

Musta, *Ambudhar*, *Megha*, *Ghana*, *Rajakaseruka*, *Bhadramusta*, *Varaha*, *Abda*, *Gangeya*, *Kuruwindaka*, *Jimuta*, *Vrishdhvankshi*, *Jalada*, *Balahaka*, *Must*, *Varidhara*, *Mustaha*, *Meghakaya*, *Pindamusta*, *Vishadhvansi*, *Bhadra*, *Varida*, *Ambhoda*, *Nirada*, *Amra*,

Vrahi, *Gunja*, *Granthi*, *Bhadrakasi*, *Kaseru*, *Krodeshta*, *Kuruvinde*, *Sugandhi*, *Granthila*, *Hima*, *Vanya*, *Rajakaseru*, *Kacchotha*, *Mustak*, *Varida nama*, *Nagara*, *Bhadramustak*, *Meghnama*, *Vrishabhaksha*, *Kroda*, *Gangeyi*, *Bhadramust*, *Vrahaad*, *Pithar*, *Pindamustaka*, *Purnakoshtha*, *Bhadrahansa*, *Prachya*, *Kalapadhra*, *Paripelava*, *Valeya*.

Sanskrit synonyms of *Mustak* in different *Nighantus*

S.N.	NAME	NIGHANTUS															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1.	<i>Musta</i>	+		+		+	+				+				+	+	
2.	<i>Megh</i>	+		+			+						+				
3.	<i>Abda</i>	+		+								+		+	+		
4.	<i>Ambudhar</i>	+										+	+				
5.	<i>Ghan</i>	+	+	+			+				+		+	+			
6.	<i>Rajakaseruka</i>	+	+			+	+						+				
8.	<i>Vraha</i>	+				+											
9.	<i>Bhadramusta</i>	+		+							+		+	+			+
10.	<i>Gangey</i>	+		+		+						+	+			+	
11.	<i>Jimuta</i>	+		+													
12.	<i>Kuruwindaka</i>	+	+			+	+						+				
13.	<i>Jalada</i>	+														+	
14.	<i>Vrishdhvankshi</i>	+														+	
15.	<i>Balahaka</i>	+															
16.	<i>Must</i>	+	+		+						+	+		+			
17.	<i>Varidhara</i>		+														
18.	<i>Mustaha</i>		+														
19.	<i>Meghakhaya</i>		+									+					
20.	<i>Pindmusta</i>		+			+										+	

		<i>Veerya-Sheet</i>			
5.	<i>Kaiyadev Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Katu, Kashay Veerya-Sheet</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta, Rakta vikar nasak</i>	<i>Grahi, Agni Deepak, Jwar, Trishna, Aruchi, Krimi</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Slok. 1357-1358</i>
6.	<i>Bhavprakash Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu, Tikta, Kashay Veerya- Sheet</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta</i>	<i>Raktakop, Trishna, Jwar, Aruchi, Krimi</i>	<i>Bh.Ni.Karpuradi varga. slok. 92-94</i>
7.	<i>Gunaratanmala</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu, Tikta, Kashay Veerya- Sheet</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta,Rakta vikar</i>	<i>Jwar, Aruchi, Trishna, Jantu nasak, Deepan,Pachan</i>	<i>Gu. Ra. Karpuradi varga. (pg.117)</i>
8.	<i>Laghu Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Katu, Kashay</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta, Rakta</i>	<i>Sangrahi, Agni Deepak, Twak rog, Shosh, Arsh, Atisar</i>	<i>La.Ni.96-98 (pg.24)</i>
9.	<i>Saligram Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Kashay</i>	<i>Kaph,Pitta, Rakta</i>	<i>Medhya, Jwar, Krimi, Atisar, Vrana, Daha, Kandu, Aam shool, Gharmah</i>	<i>Sa. Ni. Karpuradi varga. (Pg-57)</i>
10.	<i>Nighantu Adarsh</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu,Tikta, Kashay Veerya- Sheet Vipak- Katu</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta</i>	<i>Jwar,Atisar, Aruchi,Trishna, Daha</i>	<i>Ni.Ad. Mustadi varg (pg.707)</i>
11.	<i>Shankara Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Kashay</i>	<i>Kaph, Pitta, Rakta</i>	<i>Jwar, Krimi, Atisar, Vrana, Daha, Aam shool</i>	<i>Sh.Ni. (pg.141)</i>
12.	<i>Priya Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Katu</i>		<i>Grahi, Deepan, Pachan, Aam pachan, Jwar, Aruchi, Grahani</i>	<i>Pr. Ni. Shatpushapadi varga. slok.42</i>
13.	<i>Rajaballabha Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Vataghna</i>	<i>Grahi, Deepanam</i>	<i>Raj.Ba.6.Aushadhashraya parikshed slok.71</i>

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In *Charak Samhita*, *Mustak* described under various classes and varga such as *Mahakshasyas* (multifunctional) *Lekhniya Mahakashaya* (reducing and eliminating excess fats and toxins), *Stanyashodhana Mahakashaya* (improper lactation and disorders), *Trishna Nigrahana Mahakashaya* (Morbid thirst retaining), *Tripathighna Mahakashaya* (Pseudo contentment). *Musta* a very potential plant carries potential qualities and used in various formulations to pacify doshas and rejuvenate systems. Therefore, the plant is used singularly and in combinations for formulations such as *Chyavanprasha*, *Sadangapaniya*, *Navayas Churna*, *Punarnava Mandura*, etc. *Sushruta Samhita* well explained the formulations as *Kalyanaka Ghrita*, *Mahatikta Ghrita*, and *Navayas Lauha* indicated in *Pittaja* disorders, anaemia, and chronic fevers. *Ashtanga hridaya* and *Ashanga Sangraha* also recommended in various formulations such as *Pippalayadi ghrut*, *Jivantayadi ghrut*, *Bala tail*, and *Brahma Rasayan*. Other *Samhitas* and *Chikitsa Grantha*, *Rasaratna Sammucchaya*, as *Chandrakala rasa*, *Neelkanth rasa*, *Yograj guggul* have been recommended in disorders. During review *Mustak* was found with description of *Tikta*, *Katu*, *Kasaya rasa* in all *Nighantus*, *Laghu - ruksha guna*, *Sheet veerya* and carry *Kapha* and *Pitta Shamaka* properties.

CONCLUSION

The review of classical *Ayurveda* focuses the *Mustak* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) as a highly valued and potential herb known for its multifaceted quality and

therapeutic applications. Across various *Ayurvedic* treatise such as the famous *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, and *Bhavprakash Nighantu*. *Mustak* consistently illustrated as *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Grahi*, and *Tridoshahara* properties. *Mustak* particularly praised for efficacy in managing disorders related to the gastrointestinal tract, fever, and abnormal gynaecological conditions. The classical texts also recognize *Mustak's* utility in external applications for inflammatory conditions and as a part of various polyherbal formulations. Its *Rasa* (taste) is primarily *Tikta* and *Katu*, with *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna* and a *Katu Vipaka*, making it suitable for managing *Kapha* and *Pitta* disorders. Consequently, *Mustak* holds a prominent place in *Ayurvedic* pharmacopeia, not only as a stand-alone drug but also as a supportive herb in compound formulations. This literature review reinforces the herb's broad spectrum therapeutic utility and provides a strong foundation for further scientific validation and clinical exploration of its traditional uses.

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